

Practice Abstract no. 34

Consumers & citizens' views on enablers to address personal data sharing concerns

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

This practice abstract discusses consumers/ citizens' views on the enablers to address personal data sharing concerns.

- **User-centred data practices and privacy protection:** Organisations should prioritise client needs over commercial interests (e.g., aggressive marketing, data gathering), ensuring easier data storage location access and enforcing privacy rules..
- **Enhanced transparency and informed consent:** Emphasis was placed on informed consent, transparent consumer rights, data use, and data integrity. This requires user-friendly privacy statements that accurately reflect data collection and usage, and a way to monitor this data..
- **Improved data management and regulation:** Participants want clearer, simpler regulations that protect consumers without hindering innovation. The general opinion was that GDPR's complexity has made it ineffective, highlighting the need for more intensive public education on data exploitation.
- **Empowering users with control over data and traceability:** It was reiterated that users can benefit from better and easier tools to manage their data and address their privacy concerns (e.g. revoking access from different services). Furthermore, it is important to be able to trace the flow of data, from the original data processor to any other subsequent processors.
- **Addressing the existing gap between evolving technologies and existing regulations:** Participants agreed that technology is evolving at a pace far quicker than the framework that regulates it. AI was highlighted as a prominent example. While regulation must be put in place and play its role, it is important that it does not jeopardise the opportunity for innovation.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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